

The Manifestation of Images of Violence in the Educational Environment

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Abstract:

This article presents data on the manifestations of violence in the educational process, on the types of violence, the degree of protection from violence, on forms of violence and manifestations of violence.

Keywords: psychological violence, violent syndrome, physical violence, protection level, aggression, interpersonal communication, personal anxiety.

Introduction. In the work of Russian researchers and practitioners in various fields, there is no single approach to the definition of the concepts of "violence" and "abuse", in addition, there are many other concepts that are used to describe the same problem. For example, abuse, coercion, exploitation, child abuse syndrome, control and manipulation of their behavior. In most cases, people are subject to only a small percentage of cases where violence harms human health, namely the Criminal Code. When people experience violence and do not consider it violent, there are many misconceptions, since they perceive violence as the norm.

In 1999, the World Health Organization proposed the following definition of child abuse: rape is physical or emotional abuse, sexual abuse, neglect, commercial, or others that cause real or potential harm to a child's health.

Literature analysis. The problem of the psychology of violence 20 income the most modern competition in World psychology since the 80s is a wide Way (D. Levinson, J. Cobrin, D. Finkelhor, D. Ivaniek, K. Bron, R. Lang, E. Miller et al. In domestic psychology, this issue is relatively young (I. A. Alekseeva, S. L. Bratchenko, E. N. Volkova, T. L. Safronova, E. T. Sokolova, E. I. Tsimbal et al. To date, in this indicated area of psychology, it has been mentioned that the problem is that the only appearance of the field does not exist, a complete terminological and conceptual apparatus has not been developed.[1]

Forms of violence are diverse, conditionally they are divided into economic, social, political, ideological, physical types.[2].

In the current era, three frameworks are often used to refer to the types or types of exposure to violence, to which specifically designed research programs, relief and prevention programs have been developed and implemented.

The first typology will be based on the characteristics of the object of violence. It has been shown that such characteristics can include age (as an example, violence aimed at Children and the elderly), gender (violence aimed at women and girls), health status (violence aimed at disabled or incapacitated), nationality, social status, profession and other characteristics.

The second basis of classification can be the social environment or sphere in which violence occurs. In this context, domestic violence and institutional violence (school violence, boarding school violence, organizational environment, etc. Thus, domestic violence refers to aggressive and hostile actions towards family members, as a result of which violence can cause harm, injury, discrimination to a person, sometimes fatal.

The third classification is based on the nature of violent actions. There are four main types of child abuse - physical abuse, sexual abuse, psychological (psycho-emotional) abuse, and neglect of children's basic needs-categorized into types of abuse.

In addition to the main four types of violence, there are other types that have other bases for classification. For example, economic violence refers to violence applied to women and children in a family, seen in achieving one's own livelihood and depriving one of economic control over a woman.

Discussion. In the educational environment, psychological violence is manifested in different manifestations. These include: screams, insults, wrongful accusations, ridicule, intimidation, disregard for the student's needs, a demonstrative display of dislike. In such cases, students are always criticized, then offended, never praised (or praised them in a very rare case), they are not encouraged, the child's opinion is not listened to, his inability to pay, his stupidity and others are constantly remembered. Most often, such situations occur with strangers, which seriously affects the child. Sometimes an educator deliberately taunts and insults people close to him in order to humiliate and offend the student even more. Studies have shown that the manifestation of violence affects the mental development of a person.

At each psychological age, the characteristic of the norm of development is determined by four components:

- social status of development, those characteristics of the environment (in the broad sense of the word), where a person lives and his attitude to it;
- leading activities in which new features of human development are formed;
- contradictions that occur during the development process;
- individual neoplasms as the results of solving these contradictions.

L.S.Vigotsky wrote: "by the beginning of each age period, it should be recognized that the child and the reality that surrounds him, first of all, a completely special, this age-specific, exclusive, original and unique relationship between the social environment arises." We call this relationship a social state of development at a certain age. The social state of development is the starting point for all dynamic changes that occur in development during a certain period.

It defines complete forms and path, after which the child receives new personal characteristics, choosing them from social reality, as the main source of development, the path that becomes a social person.[3]. Thus, the social state of development as the main condition for the development

of a child is not only the features of the life environment, but also the features of experience, the relationship of the child with the surrounding world and people. "The modality of this experience (what it is - positive or negative, excessive or initiating action) is determined by the peculiarities of the attitude towards the child by adults [4]:

The manifestation of violence in the educational environment becomes ambiguous as characteristic features of the social state of development. Important personality affects the formation of neoplasms. Adolescent Psychology researchers note significant psychological characteristics, the formation of which occurs during a certain period of ontogenesis [9].

Many of them are deformed in interpersonal interactions under the influence of forms of violence. Most often, psychological violence occurs in educational institutions, which causes emotional stress in the victim [5], disrupts self-image and prevents the formation of personality, and role differentiation [6], reduces self-esteem, leads to deformation of interpersonal forms of communication, affects the system of value orientations and the construction of life strategies [7], reduces mental health indicators, primarily social and emotional aspects [8].

Such a child has difficulties in socialization: he tries to avoid relationships with other people. The opposite often happens-other children avoid being friends with victims of abuse because they fear they will become victims of abuse themselves, saying, "as your friend is, so is you". It follows from the result that the development of relationships carried out among individuals can cause problems for victims, and their rejection from the educational institution can often be extrapolated to other areas of relations in a social situation.

The most important aspect of pedagogical activity is the regulation of interpersonal relationships between students in terms of prevention and correction of forms of violence and the reflexive assessment of their relationship with students and colleagues in order to identify and assess the presence of elements.

Both educators and students have been found to use one-of-a-kind forms of psychological abuse. The intensity of the use of types of psychological violence between peers is higher than that of Educators, which is determined by the nature of the subjects of interaction: peers, the teacher's social relationships. Pedagogical communication is more formalized, regulated by professional standards and more subject to social control. The most common manifestation of psychological violence in an educational environment is discrimination against the honor and dignity of the student. In the educational environment, significant differences were found in the psychological characteristics of adolescents who are protected from psychological abuse at high and low levels. Students of these groups differ in the degree of severity of each hardness component, as well as in the degree of endurance in general; in terms of self-esteem and level of activity; values such as "self-development", "achievement", "value orientations", "self-esteem", and "self-acceptance" scales are defined in the self-expression test; values such as "self-development", "achievements, self-identity preservation", as well as significant differences in life such as "education and education"; I-real and I-ideal content in doubt and egocentrism indicators; levels of social anxiety, aggressiveness, and rigidity can be identified.

In the educational environment, the psychological characteristics of adolescents who are protected from psychological violence at a high and low level are determined. Students with high levels of psychological security protection will have a sense of satisfaction that they recognize as individuals with positive status and socially desirable characteristics. They are characterized by good self-control, the ability to follow the line of behavior adopted, regardless of any situation. They are open and friendly, confident, see the world as friendly and generous, which causes benevolent behavior. They are characterized by a holistic perception of the world, they fully experience the current moment of their life, they are characterized by the independence of values and behavior from external influences, are characterized by a desire for self-development. In the structure of value

orientations, the most important thing for them will be their achievements and Development, their high financial situation, all of which will be harmonized with the priority of education among the spheres of life. They see self-improvement in developing leadership qualities, increasing flexibility in behavior, and reducing suspicion. This group of adolescents is characterized by the ability to anticipate the consequences of people's behavior, which quickly recognize the change in the meaning of the sentence in the verbal response of the individual, depending on the context of the situation. The usual psychological defense mechanism for them is rationalization. Viz. they often seek a rational basis for justifying behavior as well as impulsive behavior. They are less anxious, aggressive and reactive.

Adolescents with a low level of protection against psychological violence in an educational environment perceive what is happening to them as an insoluble problem, their reaction to Psycho-traumatic situations is a feeling of helplessness. They underestimate themselves, their behavior often depends on external circumstances. Most importantly, they seek to defend their opinions and recognize their achievements in society. For them, the most important thing is the field of hobbies, and in the composition of personal motivational components, it is characteristic that the importance of training and education for them decreases, which is in harmony with the desire for a higher level of material well-being. This group of teenagers want to improve their personality by enhancing dominance, independence in personality traits, while reducing hostility. The usual psychological defense mechanism for them is projection, and the described characteristics are combined with increased situational aggression.

Result. In the educational environment, psychological abuse manifestations were found to be more common in boys than in girls. Girls are more likely to show psychological abuse by their peers and boys by teachers.

Distribution of testers by stage of Education (n=100)

№	Stages of Education	Number	%
1	Stage 1	15	15,0
2	Stage 2	29	29,0
3	Stage 3	56	56,0
	Jami:	100	100,0

In our research work, 100 student girls from Step 1 to step 3 were selected. Of these, 1 student girl participated in 1 Bashkortostan (15%), 29 (29.0%) in Phase 2, and 56 (56.0%) in Phase 3 (Table 1).

Figure 1 information about the testers

This survey was conducted by Ch.D. Developed by Spielberger, it serves to determine the level of situational anxiety (VX) as well as personality-related anxiety (SHX). Yu.L. Because of its modification by Hanin, it is called the “Spielberger Hanin survey”. The survey consists of 40 taskids – sentences. Situational or reactive anxiety is characterized by feelings that are subjectively

experienced: tension, anxiety, anxiety, irritability. This condition occurs as an emotional reaction to a stressful situation and can vary in intensity and dynamism over time.

Interpretive statistics on anxiety indicators (n=100)

Specification	N	Minimum	Max.	Mean	Standard deviation	Asymmetry	Exess
Reactive Anxiety	100	30,00	63,00	44,1400	6,82985	,372	-,152
Personal anxiety	100	34,00	75,00	51,7700	6,75974	,180	,671

On the situational anxiety scale of the "reactive and situational anxiety" methodology, minimal received 30 points, a maximum of 63 points, the average value on this indicator and the standard deviation consisted of 44.1 ±6.82, that is, from 37.2 to 50.9 points were considered the norm. Consists of asymmetry (a=0.372) and excess (E = -0.152). The results showed weakly expressed right-sided positive asymmetry and weak negative excess.

The minimum score on the "personal anxiety" scale is 34, the maximum is 75, the average value on this indicator and the standard deviation is 51.7 + 6.75, that is, 58.45 and 44.95 points are the norm. Consists of asymmetry (a=0.18) and excess (a = 0.671). The results are observed with weakly expressed right-sided positive asymmetry and weak excess.

A. Assinger's interpretive statistics on aggression (n=100)

Specification	N	Minimum	Max.	Mean	Standard deviation	Asymmetry	Exess
Aggression	100	26,00	50,00	39,6000	4,32283	-,419	,593

A. This assinger test can help determine how correct (open) an individual is in a relationship with their colleagues and how easy it is for them to communicate with him. To determine the specificity of the answers, it is possible to conduct a conversation between colleagues that evaluates each other. This helps determine how accurate their self-assessment is.

Determination of the degree of conflict questionnaire (n=100)

Conflict	100	,00		36,00	19,6500	5,12150	,176	2,697
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Questionnaire for determining the level of self-control in communication. This survey was conducted by the American psychologist M. Designed by Snyder, it serves to explore how strongly an individual can control themselves during communication.

Level of concern survey

№	Specification	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	P (ishonch darajasi)
1	R	,882	,418
2	Sh	,607	,854

In our research work, we can observe that the indicators of selective Spielberger – Hanin anxiety detection questionnaires are consistent with the law of normal distribution. ($Z=,882$, $p>0.05$, $Z=,854$; $p>0.05$). The following table shows the results of the taxile. In the subsequent laying process, it is recommended to use parametric criteria.

Aggression poll

№	Specification	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	P (ishonch darajasi)
1	A	1,348	0,53

Controversy poll

№	Specification	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	P (ishonch darajasi)
1	N	1,132	,154

Differences in Phase 1 to phase 3 cross section

(N=100 based on the Dispersion analysis criterion)

Specification	Training stages	№	Mean	Standard deviation	F	P
Reactive Anxiety	Stage 1	15	40,8000	7,32120	10,302	,000***
	Stage 2	29	41,0000	5,31171		
	Stage 3	56	46,6607	6,42234		
	Jami:	100	44,1400	6,82985		
Personal anxiety	Stage 1	15	53,0000	7,76439	2,278	,108
	Stage 2	29	49,5517	5,64159		
	Stage 3	56	52,5893	6,85639		
	Jami:	100	51,7700	6,75974		

In the Phase 3 cross section of our research work from Step 1, reliable discrepancies were found on the reactive Anxiety Index ($F=10,302$; $p<0,001$). Discrepancies in the Phase 1 to phase 3 cross section have also been found to be reliable discrepancies in the individual Anxiety Index. ($F= 2.28$; $p< 0.108$).

Differences in Phase 1 to phase 3 cross section

(N=100 based on the Dispersion analysis criterion)

Specification	Training stages	№	Mean	Standard deviation	F	P
Aggression	1-bosqich	15	40,2000	5,12975	1,562	,215
	2-bosqich	29	38,4138	5,03216		
	3-bosqich	56	40,0536	3,60515		
	Jami:	100	39,6000	4,32283		
Conflict	1-bosqich	15	20,4000	3,94244	11,925	,000***
	2-bosqich	29	22,8966	5,44023		
	3-bosqich	56	17,7679	4,34424		

Relationship by type of testers
(N=100 based on Pearson criterion analysis)

Specification	Reactive anxiety	Personal anxiety
Reactive anxiety	1	,197*
Personal anxiety	,197*	1
Aggression	,122	-,241*
Conflict	-,188	-,165

At the next stage of our study, it was analyzed that there is a correlation relationship between the results of the selected methodological scales in students from the 1st to the 3rd year. In particular, the increased situational anxiety in these types of testers would cause an increase in personal anxiety, ($r=,612$; $p<0.612$).

In particular, personal anxiety was analyzed, the presence of a correlation relationship between the results of the methodological scales obtained in students. The fact that situational anxiety decreases in these types of testers would cause a decrease in personal anxiety. ($r = ,197^*$, $p < 1$).

Conclusion. The purpose of this study was to study the impact of psychological violence in the educational environment on the psychological characteristics of students. The object of the study is students of a certain age and social group, the subject of the study is the study of the psychological characteristics of students with different levels of protection against psychological violence in the environment of higher educational education.

Prior to the empirical study, a theoretical analysis of the results of previous works on developmental psychology, as well as related social sciences, aimed at describing the phenomenon of psychological violence, was carried out. In this, the problem of psychological security situation has helped to determine its reflection in the work on overcoming stress, in the study of the level of resilience and the state of personal potential, the concept of resilience, which depends on the concept of security, is understood as a successful adaptation of an individual and a stage of development. In the context of unfavorable conditions. As a result of the analysis of the literature, it became possible to characterize the peculiarities of the development of psychological disorders in the aftermath of violence in adolescence, to characterize the features of the forms and consequences of psychological violence in the educational environment. The range of these consequences is very wide, the manifestation of which can be observed in the Cognitive, Affective and behavioral areas. As a result, our study was based on the idea of the priority of psychological violence in traumatization in all other forms of violence.

In preparation for practical training, a questionnaire was developed to learn how to protect against psychological violence in an educational environment. Adolescents with different levels of protection against psychological violence in an educational environment. In the process of work, the research goal was achieved. As a result of the study, the research goals are carried out in a consistent way, the content of its concept on the protection of a teenager from psychological violence in an educational environment is determined based on the resulting theoretical analysis. Groups of adolescents with a low and high level of protection against psychological violence are characterized, the gender identity of protection against psychological violence is characterized in the educational environment. The empirical study required an in-depth analysis of the problem, as a result of which promising areas of study of the personal characteristics of adolescents with varying degrees of protection against psychological violence were determined. The study carried out will be the selection and analysis of individual components that affect the level of psychological security of students in the process of the educational environment during the study. Advanced scientific research areas can be based on their goals and objectives to expand research on the level of

protection against psychological violence in the educational environment and to deepen analysis on this topic.

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